

¿La semi-colonia? Reflexiones sobre el nexo entre lo decolonial y lo neoimperial

The Semi-Colony? Thinking Through the Decolonial / Neo-Imperial Nexus

Carole Boyce Davies ¹

¹Cornell University, Africana Studies and English, Africana Studies and Research Center. Ithaca, New York, EUA.

Recibido: 11/10/2023
Aceptado: 21/12/2023

RESUMEN

La obra creativa de artistas y escritores del Caribe ha sido crucial para configurar el pensamiento decolonial en toda la región y en las diásporas. Este ensayo profundiza en el concepto de «semi-colonia» desde la perspectiva del análisis literario y los estudios sobre diáspora africana a través de una relectura de los símbolos en el poema «Negus» de Kamau Brathwaite (*The Arrivants*, 222-224). En este ensayo, que explora el nexo entre lo colonial, lo decolonial y lo neocolonial, la autora parte deliberadamente de lo literario y se adentra en el pensamiento teórico (inspirado en la obra de Lenin *El Imperialismo: La Fase Superior del Capitalismo*, entre otras fuentes); y finalmente, analiza las alternativas que ofrecen algunas personalidades de la política en la actualidad en el marco de un nuevo paradigma de liderazgo caribeño. El análisis literario de la autora y la lectura de la disposición lingüística del poema también contribuyen a las teorías de la colonialidad del poder para criticar la descolonización inconclusa, que contempla la colonización político-psicológica y político-económica de las infraestructuras sociales caribeñas.

Palabras clave: Caribe; semi-colonia; teoría literaria; decolonial; neocolonial; diáspora africana.

ABSTRACT

The creative work of artists and writers in the Caribbean has been crucial in shaping the decolonial thought throughout the region and in the diasporas. This essay elaborates on the concept of the “semi-colony” from the perspective of literary analysis and African diaspora studies through a reading of symbols in Kamau Brathwaite’s poem “Negus” (The Arrivants, 222-224). Exploring the colonial / decolonial / neocolonial nexus, the essay begins deliberately with the literary; it pursues some of the theoretical thinking (drawing from Lenin’s Imperialism: The Highest Stage of Capitalism, among other sources); finally, it presents options in the current political incarnations of a new Caribbean leadership paradigms. The author’s literary analysis and reading of the linguistic arrangement of the poem also contributes to theories of the coloniality of power to critique the unfinished decolonization, which looks at the political-psychological and the political-economic colonization of the Caribbean social infrastructures.

Keywords: Caribbean; semi-colony; literary theory; decolonial; neocolonial; African diaspora.

Introduction

With fields like literary studies, African Diaspora Studies and Black Women's Writing in international dimensions as my primary areas of inquiry, you will not be surprised that what follows moves through these areas as it pursues an ongoing search for the language to articulate and clarify our historical and ongoing realities. Framed as thinking through the decolonial/neocolonial nexus, it begins deliberately with the literary; pursues some of the theoretical thinking on the subject; and finally presents some options in the current political incarnations of a new Caribbean leadership paradigm based on my *Black Women's Rights. Leadership and the Circularities of Power* (2022).

Refashioning Futures: "I Must Be Given Words"

I was always taken by Kamau Brathwaite's poem "Negus" (*The Arrivants*, 222-224) for its attempt to express poetically a certain stuttering which captures the weight one often feels in the inability to release the full content of a powerful declaration. This powerful declaration, decolonial in its intent mirrors poetically the struggle to articulate fully the critique of the incompleteness of emancipation and/or independence from European colonialism and the looming imperial US presence. It also presents the struggle to find the language to name the residual effects of colonialism and therefore the ongoing coloniality still experienced in the Caribbean.

The poet moves through several rejections and negations before literally landing on the semi-colony. Here is some of that movement with which we accompany the poet through to that realization of incompleteness.

It is not
It is not
It is not enough to be free
Of the red white and blue
Of the drag, of the dragon

it is not
it is not
it is not enough
it is not enough to be free
of the whips, principalities and powers
where is your kingdom of the Word?

The echo of Alejo Carpentier's critique of the Haitian Revolution in his *The Kingdom of This World* (1949) is evident. Sadly it has contemporary implications given the repetitive and exacerbated current crises in Haiti. For the lack of realization of the intent of the Haitian Revolution still troubles definitions of Black realities globally, replaced by a consistent and ever expanding deferral to another generation again. It is useful to begin the Caribbean semi-colony experience with the historical precedent of Haiti which claimed its independence in 1804 with an open door to the rest of the Black world across the Americas, as an independent republic. But after a little more than 20 years French imperialism reasserted its grip on Haiti and reduced it to semicolonial status with its adjoining plunder by way of debt peonage. US imperialism facilitated the French assault by ignoring Haiti as a sovereign state until 1862. And into the 20th century with full scale occupation of Haiti for nearly 20 years and continued economic control, Haiti technically became a semi-colony, and indeed a crystal ball into the future of the Caribbean in view of Western imperialism.

Thus, after moving through a series of negations in its ongoing critique of the felt limitations of flag independence, of the 1960's, we have the poet's demand:

I
must be given words to shape my name
to the syllables of trees

I
must be given words to *refashion futures*¹
like a healer's hand

And finally to the key verse that drives this thematic aspect of my presentation:

*It is not
it is not
it is not enough
to be pause, to be hole
to be void, to be silent
to be semicolon, to be semicolony;*

There are several words on which we can linger in this poetic masterpiece, ("pause," "hole," "void," "silent") but the need to "refashion futures" is salient as well, for its link to the idea of decoloniality

¹ All highlights are mine. (A. N).

with its demand for the re-creation of a world free of these continuing exploitations and dominations.

According to most grammarians, stronger than a comma but not as definite as a period or full stop, the bane of undergraduate writing instructors and students, the semi-colon plays that intermediary role all the time, joining clauses, separating lists of ideas, and bridging between two independent clauses

But the irony in extending the semi-colon with just a "y" to give us a semi-colony has an allied function with our current reality of not having quite a full stop or ending to colonialism. Instead colonialism lingers still with perhaps a slight or troubling pause, an interruption via public performance, like the formal public promise to return African art from European museums, that never fulfills its intended end ever.

We learn further that the semi-colon is an inheritance from a particular form of class-based English –essentially tonal expression– but as the literary (middle-class, schooled) version, it becomes codified in its current grammatical form. Thus, the coding of the semi-colon is not as much of a stop as a colon, certainly not as much as a full-stop, but more than a comma it signals that inbetweenity which masks its function. Commas are useful for flow because they allow clauses to be built and juxtapositions to be made and additional ideas can develop that way. But semi-colons kind of assert a division in thought, less than colons; more suitable to a listing of separate items.²

My key assertion here is that the linguistic arrangement has a parallel political assertion, as it mirrors that would be *transformation* following quasi independence, limited as well by the very grammar through which we think. Thus, for Kamau Brathwaite it was necessary always to undermine these received frames by making his poetic juxtapositions without the need for creating paragraphs which in fields like academic history demand a particular orientation, a particular narrative way in which even radical thought must be expressed.

Poetry instead can enact its subversion of these ordered systems –do things with language, actually create new language. So, as we consider the semi-colon and semi-colony juxtaposition, we can similarly embrace the poet's model to establish a kinetic relation in our imaginations at the same time and let the two frames spark the need for new ideas, new language, new questions and above all new realities.

Interestingly the early analyses of this poem, as attempted by Caribbean neo-colonial critiques focused on the quality of the poem, made fun of the "stammer" just as some used to make fun of those with that actual speech defect. For Eddie Baugh in "Poetry as Ritual: Reading Kamau Brathwaite" [*Journal of West Indian Literature* 8:1(October, 1998):1-9] pursues this discussion, citing one scholar who suggested the following paraphrase:

² I arrived at this final summary of what the semi-colon means in grammar in conversation with Elaine Savory Fido Jones my co-editor of *Out of the Kumbia. Caribbean Women and Literature*, 1990, based on her analysis of her English grammar school educational experience.

"It is not enough to have constitutional independence if we remain culturally and economically dependent upon colonial and neo-colonial sources, and if independence means despoiling the landscape and dis[possessing the peasantry]" (4) [*Introduction to the Study of West Indian Literature*, page 134 cited in Baugh].

Perhaps a fair enough but banal summary, it nonetheless misses all the play with words and is precisely the point though for it is certainly not as dramatically charged as the poet's version. Thus, for Baugh the poem has to be read as ritual and its ritualistic re-reading which those who have heard Kamau present his poetry know that the poet did so magnificently. In this case, he provides the incremental rhythm which allows meaning to unfold. Thus, Baugh concludes: "The experience of reading and re-reading it will also be a process of uncovering the meaning, we must at the same time read as if the meaning is given, and we are participants in the ritual, enacting the meaning (8)."

Of course, so much has happened in terms of the breadth, politics and intent of performance poetry since those limited analyses some twenty years ago. As indeed since then, rather than being an outlier, Kamau Brathwaite (1930-2020) became a leader in poetic innovation using instead the linguistic rhythms of the Caribbean. In addition to creating now standard rhythmic tropes: alliteration, reverberating echoes, code switching and fracturing of the language of standard English deliberately re-deploying the "broken English" insult with its play on words, he also simultaneously articulated the colonial dislocation and disruption of its subjects as they also attempted to re-territorialize received language. That creative-theoretical use of poetry which Kamau mastered now has visible intent say in the poetry of a range of succeeding poets.

So the poetic translation into theoretical language is precisely where the poet has an advantage, as being able to say concisely in poetic form what scholars spend pages to analyze and thereby meets the current generation of resisting-readers. In this context, we can never lose sight of the creative-theoretical innovations that were Kamau Brathwaite's. For his was a quest to still find the language which leads directly into his asking for open passage to speak, to create, to act, to transform to *refashion futures* which in the end is what independence was supposed to do and indeed what the writer does with words.

And this is where I want to go next without losing sight of the creative-theoretical innovations that were Kamau Brathwaite's. We can conclude this section by noting that languaging the "semi-colony" is powerful for it is a simultaneous critique of the colonality of language as of actual lingering colonialism and re-opens for us another analytical frame. Kamau, with his repetition of words or portions of words and the entry into an Afro-Caribbean tonal language, gives these syllables different layered meanings as he juxtaposed them with the actuality of the colonial life in a way that transgressed English which as a language has lost most of that orality through the over-determining of the scribal. But trying to escape the "colony" remains the challenge for, as we

learned from Ngugi wa Thiong'o (1986), colonialism was as much a linguistic operation as much as it was a capitalist/economic one.

The Decolonial/Neo-Imperial Nexus as an Early Caribbean Experience

An early assessment of our current situation comes by way of Claudia Jones who in her "Imperialism and the British West Indies" (1958) was definite in her recognition of how American Imperialism was going to play out in the Caribbean. Of course, she was right in concluding that: "We know, of course, that as its foundations totter, imperialism seeks more flexible methods of governing the colonies and seeks to devise new means to camouflage its rule, (*Claudia Jones. Beyond Containment*, 160). This she saw as possible because." The growth of American economic and political influence in the West Indies was facilitated by the establishment in 1942 of an Anglo-American Caribbean commission..." which aided American monopolists who have been seizing possession of the natural resources of the West Indies." (157).

Thus, as Monica Jardine and I had concluded in "Imperial Geographies and Caribbean Nationalism: at The Border Between *A Dying Colonialism* and U.S. Hegemony." (2003), "the possibility of a modern Caribbean nation was thereby caught at its origins between a retreating and a rising region-wide European imperialism: the first bowing before the military and economic expansion of the United States in the Caribbean region, after the U.S. takeover of the Spanish Empire following 1890; the second seeking to accommodate a series of dying colonialisms with the need for a modern nationalism." (152). According to Colin Palmer's *Eric Williams and the Making of the Modern Caribbean* (Chapter 4 on "The Golden Handshake), Eric Williams then prime minister of Trinidad and Tobago at the end of formal colonialism was the only leader to refuse a monetary pittance which was to be spent on purchasing British goods. Williams "invok[ed] the specter of colonial exploitation and its relationship to the construction of the British economy" as insufficient and the attached strings an insult, describing the relationship. In a 1962 London School of Economics speech, as well as in a later one to West Indian students as follows:

"The West Indies are in the position of an orange. The British have sucked it dry and their sole concern today is that they should not slip and get damaged on the peel... The offer is quite unacceptable and we would prefer not to have it... [as it] amounted to aid to Britain rather than to Trinidad [and Tobago]... I do not propose to accept any concept of the Commonwealth which means common wealth for Britain and common poverty for us."

Beckles cites this in *How Britain Underdeveloped the Caribbean* as precisely the basis for reparative justice, particularly when the British have been so explicit in their intent, citing Churchill among several pieces of evidence as saying: "Our possession of the West Indies...gave us the strength, the support, but especially the capital, the wealth, at a time when no other European nation possessed such a reserve..." (7)

I was always taken by what happened to the island of Barbuda during Hurricane Irma after reading a headline that for the first time since the 1700's the island had no residents. A headline about Barbuda after two hurricanes caught my eye: "For the first time in 300 years, no one is living on Barbuda" September 15, 2007 (*USA Today*). I paused, realizing with a shock that what was being casually reported was the hey day of the transatlantic slave trade and plantation slavery. So a rhetorical question for you: What were Europeans doing in the Caribbean in 1717? Subtracting 300 years from 2017 produces 1717, a year at the height of transatlantic and plantation-bound chattel slavery. Before the arrival of Africans from the 16th to the 19th centuries, indigenous Caribs, Tainos, and Kalinagos lived on larger islands or mainland locations in South or North America; and often moved, as is done in contemporary Cuba, out of pathways of impending storms.³

Those displaced residents from Barbuda are descendants of people brought there only to be enslaved for sugar cane production and its related economics; indigenous people had been destroyed or deported to elsewhere; and contemporary tourism and property speculation continued the process. According to Beckles, "Barbuda, an island once grabbed by Christopher Cardington, imperial warlord of England, and genocidal leader who received a mandate from his King to wipe the native Kalinago people off the face of the earth, was wiped out by Irma." ⁴

As we shall see that was not the end of the story. Enter neo- imperialism as we asserted, not so much after territorial possession and settling but military and economic coordination which ensured global capitalist control. So today in between Williams' assessment and Jones predictions, in contemporary Caribbean, we see the US imperial effects fully unfolded and in the crudest of forms. For what we have today are some countries politically independent, a few republics, several still colonies, some like Barbuda being recolonized by luxury business interests.

Modern Semi-Colonies?

³ See for example Ignacio Olazagasti, "The Material Culture of the Taino Indians," in Samuel Wilson, *Indigenous Peoples of the Caribbean* and Scott Fitzpatrick, "The Pre-Columbian Caribbean: Colonization, Population Dispersal, and Island Adaptations" *PaleoAmerica* 1:4(2015): 305+

⁴ Hilary Beckles, "Irma-Maria. A Reparations Requiem for Caribbean Poverty." A Statement from the Vice Chancellor, University of the West Indies. September 26, 2017. Available on UWI and Caribbean Studies Association websites.

I moved as many of us have through multiple theorizings of the post-colonial, finding them all inadequate, too premature, and decided to linger on Achille Mbembe's (1992) definition of what he called the "post colony" possibly because he used the noun form in his However there was always a consistent critique of the idea of postness in a context when there were still so many active colonies. A friend from London, originally from Jamaica had been at home and gotten into a traffic issue for which he had to go to court and told me angrily how shocked he was that when he went to court the queen's picture was prominently displayed there. I had the same sensation upon arriving with family in the Turks and Caicos islands after having gone to the Institute of Commonwealth Studies in London to see in its lobby the huge map with all the active colonies identified. Of course we understood the theoretical break that was advanced but not the reality of the continuing Fanonian lived experience of blackness (See his *Black Skin, White Masks* for that full discussion). Across the Caribbean, several island units still maintain a more explicit older British colonial tie with photographs of the queen one of the first things that one sees prominently displayed in its airport as one enters the country. Thus, in a chapter titled "From "Post-Coloniality to Uprising Textualities," in *Migrations of the Subject*, I addressed its theoretical prematurity.

But, above all, re-reading Mbembe's post-colony essay provided another concern as he identified there a very masculinist national post-colony which was actually a semi-colony, in which *half the world* in the familiar gendered framing are not really represented. Basically the history and trajectory of "half the world" discourses which was articulated via Claudia Jones which I used titularly for the chapter on her journalism, has theoretical application in this context as well. One can use this mathematical formulation of semi-ness, seeing women and black people as always the unrepresented, and therefor exploited and oppressed sector of the larger community, given the structures of state power, and the ideological function of so-called representative government. This she had clearly identified in her "We Seek Full Equality"⁵ essay though the "neglect" essay published that same year gets more citational identification. The idea of internal groups existing in semi-colonial status to a dominant nation remains. In this version of the semi-colony, half of the population is not fully represented. Thus we can say from the outset that a demographically coherent portion of any population remains a semi-colony if its labor is still colonized, triply or multiply exploited.

Moving further with the languaging of "Semi," as prefix it also means half as in semi-circle but also "almost" or "partially" "incompletely." Thus, central to black women's emancipatory politics in the early 20th century was Frances Watkins Harper 1825-1911, poet, short story, activist statement: "I know that no nation can gain its full measure of enlightenment and happiness if *one-half of it is free, and the other half fettered.*" The implications of this framing is significant though it refers largely to racial subordination and gender subordination simultaneously. I explore this more fully in *Black Women's Rights* (2022).

Thinking through the theoretics of the semi-colony, the place where it is definitely identified is in Lenin's "Imperialism, the Highest Stage of Capitalism" (1917). Lenin had argued that the "twentieth century marks the turning-point from the old capitalism to the new, from the domination of capital

⁵ All the Claudia Jones essays indicated here are published in *Claudia Jones. Beyond Containment*, Ayebia. 2011.

in general to the domination of finance capital." There he had continued: "The epoch of the latest stage of capitalism shows us that certain relations between capitalist associations group, based on the economic division of the world, while parallel to it and in connection with it, certain relations grow up between political alliances, between states, on the basis of the territorial division of the world, of the struggle for colonies, of the "struggle for spheres of influence." It is here (that he uses the language of the semi-colony, indicating as well that there are different types of semi-colonies:

Since we are speaking of colonial policy in the epoch of capitalist imperialism, it must be observed that finance capital and its foreign policy, which is the struggle of the great powers for the economic and political division of the world, give rise to a number of transitional forms of state dependence. Not only are the two main groups of countries, those owning colonies, and the colonies themselves, but also the diverse forms of dependent countries which, *politically, are formally independent, but in fact, are enmeshed in the net of financial and diplomatic dependence*, typical of this epoch. We have already referred to one form of dependence—the semi-colony. An example of another is provided by Argentina. (Chapter VI. Division of the World Among the Great Powers)

Thus in his "Critique of Imperialism" chapter we again have the language of the semi-colony which indicates that these exist in different forms or versions. Via this analysis Nkrumah's "Neocolonialism, The Last Stage of Capitalism" (1966) is a text to which one can return again for clarity as a timely assessment, 10 years or so after the first wave of African and Caribbean political independence. This he defines as "The neo-colonialism of today represents imperialism in its final and perhaps its most dangerous stage...

The essence of neo-colonialism is that the State which is subject to it is, in theory, independent and has all the outward trappings of international sovereignty. In reality its economic system and thus its political policy is directed from outside...

More often, however, neo-colonialist control is exercised through economic or monetary means. The neo-colonial State may be obliged to take the manufactured products of the imperialist power to the exclusion of competing products from elsewhere. Control over government policy in the neo-colonial State may be secured by payments towards the cost of running the State, by the provision of civil servants in positions where they can dictate policy, and by monetary control over foreign exchange through the imposition of a banking system controlled by the imperial power. (Introduction, p. 4)

So, for him, the equation is made between a conjoined neo-colonialism and neo-imperialism which re-emphasizes that we need to read colonialism as largely economic as we know the cultural analyses have been the largest volume. And today, while the theoretical languaging of neo-

colonialism comes across as dated, the same systems proliferate and actually prove Nkrumah's assertion that neo-colonialism is not old but is actually the current stage of capitalism we are experiencing.

The assumption is the move to a certain limited political independence meant that we totally miss the entrenched colonial relationship between colonies and former colonizers in which each maintain a relationship of economic dominance and therefore of colonialism. Walter Rodney had asserted something similar in his 1976 "Decolonization" essay, now a concluding chapter of the recently published *Decolonial Marxism* (2022). But even at his writing the assumption was that similar discussions were already passe. According to John McClendon, "The viewpoint that neo-colonialism is dated follows from the intellectual cultural framework that frames the matter along the line of the post-colonial or colony rather than neo-colonialism. The ideological imperative to bring clarification to the discussion is why reasserting neo-colonialism is significant. In the case of both Lenin and Nkrumah we readily understand that the foundation for colonialism (whatever its form) is imperialism. And imperialism is not just a policy of a given government rather it is a stage within the development of capitalism. Therefore, consistent anti-imperialism is a battle against capitalism, which initiates the struggle for socialism on scientific grounds."⁶

What Walter Rodney observed then was that "the overlap, this interpenetration of the existence of colonialism with the existence of neo-colonialism affects the character of decolonization in a number of ways...It affects the character of decolonization of those states which are formally non-independent, those which are still formally colonies, and it affects the character of decolonization in those areas which are normally colonies (290).

Rodney was talking about Africa in the late 1970's but one can see a similar argument mounted in the contemporary by Taiwo in *Elite Capture* when he says: "The system has never been dismantled, so while "empire" is no longer a popular term in global politics, we're still basically living it...(4). Institutions like policing created for certain aims in the colonial period which do similar things and remain constant. We can also add mass incarceration in which a fully colonized labor pool visibly exploited remains hidden in plain sight. And if we apply this analysis to the Caribbean we can also see a wide variety of visible colonial and semi-colonial relations existing relationally. The overlap between different types of semi-colonies becomes visible.

So continuing with the Caribbean as example, following the recent passing of the British monarch, Queen Elizabeth II (2022), the Jamaican political situation was readdressed as many were shocked that Jamaica remained a semi-colony still with the Royal Family as head of state, The range of others similarly situated include the Francophone Caribbean with Martinique and Guadeloupe as overseas divisions of France but definitely semi-colonies; Puerto Rico and the Virgin Islands in their relationship with the United States. A range of others like Trinidad and Tobago, though with republic status are economically colonies of US economic interests. Since we know that the economic basis of extractive colonialism, generated a range of practices, psychological, cultural,

⁶ Personal phone communication, March, 2022.

behavioral, educational we are able to attempt a wider reading of this notion of the semi-colony, as the incomplete, partial or unfinished project of decolonization.

So how are to define a semi-colony? We can say provisionally, that moving beyond the four (4) categories identified by Lenin, there are several different versions masquerading as politically independent nations. A semi-colony used to be a full-fledged political colony but now runs its political affairs with a local neo-colonial structure in place which replicates to the extreme the remaining cultural and economic structures of that prior colonial arrangement. We can also say it also refers to an internally colonized people in a larger polity who similarly have to navigate the larger colonial systems which appropriate their labor power, their land, their ability to live full lives. Largely male-dominated leadership maintain a relationship of patrimony with the economic structures of former or new imperial control as they too extract wealth for the benefit of those economic interests as they keep a certain dominance of internal peoples in place.

Linking the creative and the theoretical, which is my approach here, there are several ways one can re-define colonialism in this context. Ngugi wa Thiong'o in *Decolonizing the Mind*, 1982/1986. centralized the issue that African literature was still being written in colonial languages (6). But his assertion on colonialism following Fanon is worth repeating here:

The real aim of colonialism was to control the people's wealth: what they produced, how they produced it, and how it was distributed; to control, in other words, the entire realm of the language of real life. Colonialism imposed its control of the social production of wealth through military conquest and subsequent dictatorship. But its most important area of domination was the mental universe of the colonized, the control through culture of, how people perceived themselves and their relationship to the world. (*Decolonizing the Mind* 16)

Sylvia Tamale influenced by Quijano and his theory of the coloniality of power proposes a two-pronged approach which looks at the political and psychological colonization and the political-economic colonization is useful. Thus, she offers a Leninist assertion that "Colonialism was not just a political or cultural imposition but at its heart lay the development and export of finance capital." Quijano (2000) had asserted that "The modern world system locates its beginning in the fifteenth century and links it to capitalism. This spatial articulation of power since the sixteenth century and emergence of the Atlantic commercial circuit is theorized as the "coloniality of power"... the overall dimension of modernity, thereby distinguishing Coloniality from colonialism (60)."

A helpful discussion which thinks through the internal colonial relationships of settler colonies, is "Decolonization is Not a Metaphor" (2012) grounded in the critique of US settler colonialism, as it pertains to the Americas. They describe settler colonialism as operating through internal/external colonial modes simultaneously because there is no spatial separation between metropole and colony (5)...Not unique, the United States, as a settler colonial nation-state, also operates as an empire –utilizing *external* forms and *internal* forms of colonization simultaneous to the settler colonial project....Decolonisation in a settler context is fraught because empire settlement and

internal colony have no spatial separation. [They conclude] Each of these features of settler colonialism in the US context –empire, settlement, and internal colony– make it a site of contradictory decolonial desires (7)

A few surprisingly timely examples have been on full display recently in the United States. The passing of Queen Elizabeth which transmitted in minute detail all of the structures of empire, experienced at the level of the performative, the pomp and pageantry which is the hallmark of allegiance and practice of loyalty to a former colonizer. So while the US operates with both settler colonialism internally and imperialism externally, it nonetheless operates as a *cultural colony* in relation to Britain, i.e. even as it is a global hegemon, the United States still operates in a neo-cultural-colonial relation to the British. What would become The United States still struggling to be a coherent nation, though gaining its self-definition quite early as it did not have such a long encounter with colonialism, yet it still maintains a distinct adoration of things British from accents to academic departments called English and definitely also the high-level consuming of news related to the Royal Family and its various machinations, particularly in the conjunction of the “special relationship” both at the political and personal levels.

A Neo-Imperial/Semi-Colony?

“I must be given words to shape my name/ to the syllables of trees/I must be given words to refashion futures/ like a healer’s hand.

Further elaborating the internal colony position, African American intellectual thought has therefore sporadically engaged the notion of the semi-colony as internal colony, throughout African American history. I noted for example the titling of W.E.B. DuBois’s “small nation of people” reference with which he described Black people in the United States in the 19th century for an 1899 exhibit of American Negroes at the Paris Exposition (*A Small Nation of People. W.E.B. DuBois and African American Portraits of Progress* with essays by David Levering Lewis and Deborah Willis (Amistad, 2003).

For the Black left, the Internal Colony discourses preceded subsequent integrationist moves marked by a series of appeals to the United Nations on behalf of the Black people being victimized in the United States and recur consistently particularly in times of glaring oppression. Such is the “We Charge Genocide” petition during the era of lynching, for example which in the subtitle that spells it out: *We Charge Genocide: The Historic Petition to the United Nations for Relief From a Crime of The United States Government Against the Negro People*” (1951). It continues: “The Civil Rights Congress has prepared and submits this petition to the General Assembly of the United Nations on behalf of the Negro people in the interest of peace and democracy, charging the Government of the United States of America with violation of the Charter of the United

Nations and the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide.” Interestingly Puerto Rico is identified as a colony of the US though it was not the center of this claim:

We have not dealt here with the cruel and inhuman policy of this government toward the people of Puerto Rico. Impoverished and reduced to a semi-literate state through the wanton exploitation and oppression by gigantic American concerns, through the merciless frame-up and imprisonment of hundred of its sons and daughter, this colony of the rulers of the United States reveals in all its stark nakedness the moral bankruptcy of this government and those who control its home and foreign policies.

History has shown that the racist theory of government of the U.S.A. is not the private affair of Americans, but the concern of mankind everywhere.

This charge which covers the areas of economic genocide, physical, absence of democratic benefits in the end becomes one of a series claims culminating in the most recent international appeals following the killing of George Floyd. sent to High Commissioner Michelle Bachelet, Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) March 30, 2021. The International Commission of Inquiry on Systemic Racist Police Violence Against People of African Descent in the United States “empaneled in response to the voices of families throughout the United States who came together in the wake of the killing of George Floyd to ask the Human Rights Council to focus on this important issue. That request which included the National Council of Black Lawyers) to “undertake a global investigation of systemic racist police violence.” In its executive summary, the Commission recommended:

23. that the U.S. executive and legislative branches acknowledge that the transatlantic trade in Africans, enslavement, colonization and colonialism were Crimes against Humanity and are among the major sources and manifestations of racism, racial discrimination, Afrophobia, xenophobia and related intolerance. Past injustices and crimes against people of African descent in the U.S. must be addressed with reparatory justice.

24. The Commissioners also recommend that the U.S. Congress establish a commission to examine enslavement and racial discrimination in the colonies and the U.S. from 1619 to the present and recommend appropriate remedies. The Commissioners urge the U.S. to consider seriously applying analogous elements contained in the Caribbean Community’s Ten-Point Action Plan on Reparations, which includes a formal apology, health initiatives, educational opportunities, an African knowledge.

We already know that the US model of segregation influenced the structures of South African Apartheid, Hitler’s Nazism and Australian treatment of its indigenous peoples and the Israeli

encircling and dispossession of Palestinians. As indicated earlier, "Decolonization is not a metaphor" highlights the way that settler colonialism has continued to maintain an internal colony with the settler-native-slave triad in which Africans ended up being used to further colonize the land across the Americas. Various other complaints to the United Nations then to report the disinheritance of black subjects remain.

A return to Black left theoretics then reveals the ways that for example The Black Belt Thesis was advanced by Black cadre of the CPUSA and detailed in the essay by Claudia Jones, "On the Right to Self Determination for the Negro People in the Black Belt" (1946) which is framed as a discussion article and which reflected the varying positions of a constituency that was trying to find a pathway to "Negro" rights in the United States by asserting the right to control that particular still contested region of the United States. Using the language of "national liberation" the idea was to alleviate the conditions of black people in the US South suffering from a range of subordinations.

Given recent discussions on how to think through current realities, such as in Adom Getachew's *Worldmaking after Empire: The Rise and Fall of Self-Determination* (2019), it may be worth a re-engagement with earlier silenced conceptual formations which were also part of the post-cold-war intellectual limitations to remove analyses of class contradictions. In between the CPUSA Black belt position and the contemporary we would have only limited engagement with some of these themes such as the essays in the special issue of *The Black Scholar*: "Black Cities. Colonies or City States" in which my former colleague James Turner a year after the founding of Africana at Cornell writing "Blacks In The Cities: Land And Self-Determination" (*The Black Scholar*, April 1970). Interestingly it is kind of summary assessment of the time, published the same year and month as the burning of the first Africana center in April, 1970:

... the black community is now struggling for its self-determination as a colony against an imperialist power; conscious that any serious improvement of the condition of black people depends upon their ridding themselves of the whole parasitical white structure comprised of a huge network of absentee entrepreneurs and administrators. This network includes landlords, merchants, realtors, racketeers and politicians, union leaders, licensing and inspector bureaucrats, university and school administrators, doctors, lawyers, and policemen.

Turner cites as theoretical/political precedent James Boggs, "Manifesto for a Black Revolutionary Party" (1969), Subsequent discussions of internal colonialism have tended to be critiques of nationalism such as "The culture of "Internal Colonialism": A Marxist Perspective" (*Melus* Autumn, 1981. 8:3): 18-27) which describes the internal colony discourse as a basis for a certain Black nationalism raised by people like Amiri Baraka, the Black Panther Party though within a context of Marxist analysis it ends up being reduced to cultural nationalism. A more nuanced analysis is that historically the 'United States constituted a multi-national state with several oppressed nations inside. The process of empire expansion meant that a multiple number of people belonging to various nations came under its dominance. The forging of the oppressor nation required establishing racial distinctions based on identifying particular groups of people as white and others

as non-white. The notion of white supremacy facilitated the development of the multinational state. The oppressed nations and nationalities such as the various nations of indigenous people, African Americans, and later Hawaiians, Puerto Ricans, Guam, Alaskans, along with the English speaking Caribbean islands designated as US territories comprise the multinational body under the state power of the United States. The ideological camouflage of this reality results in the formulation of a contested multiracial nation.”

Yet the ongoing contested relationship with Latin American left possibilities as in the unrelenting Cuban embargo (media and politically framed) continues. Never having had the British form of colonialism, and gaining independence many years before the Anglophone Caribbean, the US relationships with Latin America and the Caribbean particularly because of geography still ended up being more evidently colonial as Quijano and others have described it, throughout their history signaling for sure the economic form of colonialism in which one’s business apparatus is managed by finance capital generated from a few centers. Thus we repeat here too that what is often erased or not clear is that the US and Europe continue to have existing colonies; subordinate indigenous peoples and maintain a variety of other internally colonized, semi-colonies existing in a colonial relationship to the state.

Representing Half the World

“When will leaders lead? Our people are watching, and our people are taking note,” is one of the many striking lines delivered by current prime minister of Barbados, the Honorable Mia Amor Mottley, (2018-present) as she addressed the Glasgow COP 21 Conference.⁷ Clearly conscious that this was an address about leadership in times of crisis, she addressed the predominantly white and male fellow world leaders with an assumption of her equal footing as a leader and brought forward a progressive planetary consciousness that challenged them to action on behalf of the two-thirds of the world living a global inequality that threatens humanity’s survival. “Leaders must not fail those who elect them to lead,” she added and thereby entered herself and the Caribbean on the world stage with a dynamic level of leadership not seen since the days of the decolonial struggles

⁷ The 2021 United Nations Climate Change Conference, more commonly referred to as COP26, was the 26th United Nations Climate Change conference, held at Glasgow, Scotland, October 31 to November 12, 2021. Prime Minister Mottley spoke on November 1, 2021 and her address was so powerful that it circulated worldwide and captured the strength of challenge along with the determination to enter history in a way that is ethical, politically-wise and unafraid with decolonial fervor. Her speech was replayed on multiple social media platforms and carried in newspapers worldwide. See <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2021/nov/01/digging-our-own-graves-world-leaders-speak-cop26> [accessed 11/28/2021].

leading to political independence in the 1960's. Mia Amor Mottley in 2021 as she operated with confidence on a world stage, became an internationally-recognized leader.

Two years earlier when she addressed the United Nations Climate Summit and the United Nations General Assembly on September 27, 2019, she had asserted that Caribbean islands will not survive climate change,⁸ and there had deliberately challenged the assumptions of the dominant continental countries in the north that create practices detrimental to the Caribbean region. This position was also reported in the 2022 COP conference in Egypt.⁹

In each of these scenarios Prime Minister Mottley offered, in both international contexts, one of the most affirmative of the various responses to the latest and impending environmental catastrophes but also linked the issue of climate change to ongoing issues of migration and political instability that Caribbean residents face, often from their powerful northern neighbor, the United States. Additionally, as the then current head of the Caribbean Economic Community (CARICOM), she offered a relational and historical analysis of the continuous war threats from the United States to Venezuela. Soon her words, circulated on social media and were replayed on numerous sites. Her challenge that "Our Caribbean Sea must remain a zone of peace, and for that we shall fight" rang with the eloquence and political clarity which identify her as the leading member of a new generation of women providing a new paradigm of world political leadership.¹⁰

The Caribbean exists as a series of archipelagoes of islands, therefore separated by water from each other as well as from larger continental locations in North and South America. But new definitions of the Caribbean, such as those explored in *Caribbean Spaces* (2013) and a variety of studies by Caribbean scholars, consistently describe the entire circum-Caribbean as central to an understanding of this geography. Islands in the Caribbean, especially those in the direct pathway of global currents, like Ayiti take direct blows from trade winds from Africa to the Americas. Each year Caribbean residents of islands and pathway continental locations await a metaphoric roll of the hurricane dice, unsure which will island or coastline be hit next. The same trade winds that brought Columbus to the "New World" and enslaved Africans to the Americas are the same pathways that hurricanes follow, now with a ferocity never seen before, their force credited to extreme climate change. Assertions that these mega-hurricanes result from the intense new climate patterns caused by global warming are no longer relegated to obscure science journals; this analysis now appears in newspaper articles, in magazines, on television and the world wide web. Mimi Sheller's "Caribbean Futures in the Offshore Anthropocene: Debt, Disaster, and Duration" offers a good assessment of the conjunctions of climate disaster and the unresolved histories of exploitation of Caribbean land- and seascapes.

Thus, an international reparations agenda is still active, even as countries like Britain and the United States seem mired in their self-imposed political dramas. Creating usable future plans for the

⁸ *Huffington Post*, September 23, 2019.

⁹ <https://womensagenda.com.au/latest/barbados-pm-mia-mottley-tells-cop27-there-will-be-1-billion-climate-refugees-by-2050/>

¹⁰ Most popular media such as Caribbean Today in South Florida indicate that she demonstrates the most leadership of Caribbean heads of state.

survival of people who were brought to the Caribbean, often by force, and now still live in precarious locations is a major international challenge. So, how do new paradigms of leadership instrumentalize Caribbean futures?

But how to challenge those structures and create new paradigms? I want to suggest that this is one of the models that Mia Mottley uses in her so far successful tenure as the prime minister of Barbados. In 2019, Barbados signed agreements with Ghana, West Africa establishing more African diasporic relationships¹¹ with the expressed purpose of opening up more direct transportation and communication between the continent and the diaspora. According to the report, "The agreement will help to facilitate the expansion of trade between the two countries, in terms of trade transiting through Barbados from Ghana and onward to other Caribbean and Latin America destination ports." The creative political leadership of Barbadian-American, Paule Marshall as also fellow Barbadian Kamau Brathwaite were thereby also revealed.

While Kamau Brathwaite had experienced and written poetically about the various journeys of displacement and return, but also sojourns between the Caribbean and Africa, novelist Paule Marshall, in *The Chosen Place, The Timeless People* (1984) had described a more direct and possible geographic spatial/aerial relationship to the continent, creating a different return pathway that does not always assume the presence of Europe or North America aviation routings in the journey.

The Mia Mottley Prime Ministership of Barbados, is still being written. One signature statement is relevantly indicated here though:

...this country has been forged regrettably in the bowels of discrimination cannot now want to discriminate against anybody for any reason. All must breathe. All must breathe in this world. All must breathe in this country. And to that extent Mr. Speaker...I am not going to be part of any communication that suggests that Barbados is trying to be half of who or what it is and that we are sponsoring discrimination or phobias of any type."¹²

¹¹ <https://www.abcnewsgh.com/ghana-barbados-sign-agreement-to-establish-sister-port-relationship-between-tema-bridgetown/>

¹² <https://www.livingoutloud20.com/post/exclusive-barbados-prime-minister-responds-to-report-of-lgbtq-exclusion-changes-visa-requirements?fbclid=IwAR06EJYNT9s8AjcdCsrWYP7Gxb0CxcC-bM3cM5v9WvCDyMILDaa87CDQfgo>

Full text:

"There's an issue as to who Barbados will welcome and who it will not welcome. Well, I want to say, as long as I am Prime Minister of this nation, we welcome all. Everyone. And that this country, that has been forged regrettably in the bowels of discrimination cannot now want to discriminate against anybody for any reason.

All must breathe. All must breathe in this world. All must breathe in this country.

And to that extent Mr. Speaker...the incident in which...and we get it, there's difficult discussions we must have as a nation and now is not the time to have those discussions. But what I do know, is that the

So far, Mottley has operated with competence as the Head of Caricom, 2018-2020, representing the Caribbean Economic Community at the United Nations and her country during the time of COVID-19 in impressive ways. In the meantime, she talks affirmatively to interviewers as in one of the best discussions of these problems generated by, but pre-existing COVID-19, are the vulnerable locations of the Caribbean. She describes to interviewer Christiane Amanpour¹³ (4/29/2020), the need for a new "vulnerability index" which the Commonwealth Secretariat had developed 30 years before and suggests the need for a new approach to contemporary needs.

Further advancing a new decolonial paradigm though was the recent decision by Barbados under Prime Minister Mottley's leadership to take Barbados into Republican status. This is a related action which clarified that even with popular discourses of postcoloniality, many countries in the Caribbean, including Jamaica, never completed the formal separation from the British or French political dominance. Caribbean media such as the *Jamaican Gleaner* applauded the move in its bold caption "Time To Leave The Queen... Barbados To Become Republic In 2021"¹⁴ indicating as well that the Queen is still head of state of several CARICOM countries as indicated earlier.

This decolonial move was even more dramatically symbolized in the removal of the statue of Lord Horatio Nelson from its prominence in front of Barbados Parliament building on November 17, 2020, in celebratory yet funeral-like procession to a museum quarters. According to *Huffington Post*, coming in the wake of a series of similar moves around the world, "It joins a number of other statues across the globe, including slave traders in Britain to Confederate generals in the United States, to have been hauled down as the Black Lives Matter campaign gathered momentum"¹⁵

Offering a direct critique of the residual colonial appropriative situation, Jamaica Kincaid in *A Small Place* (1988) had noted the following:

member for St. Peter has a bill before this honorable chamber that says that there shall be no discrimination on any grounds in the workplace. And that debate will probably start later today.

No discrimination on the grounds of race, no discrimination on the grounds of age, no discrimination on the grounds of color, no discrimination on the grounds of gender, no discrimination on the grounds of sexual orientation.

And the people that want to put us in a box that will allow people to be discriminated against for any reason, Mr. Speaker, that is not who we are. We are not that person. We are not that person. And we've never been. You know the irony is that this country has welcomed people for decades and centuries without being that person. This country has made people feel comfortable.

I am not going to be part of any communication that suggests that Barbados is trying to be half of who or what it is, and that we are sponsoring discrimination or phobias of any type."

¹³ <https://www.cnn.com/videos/tv/2020/04/29/amanpour-barbados-mia-mottley-coronavirus.cnn>

¹⁴ <http://jamaica-gleaner.com/article/caribbean/20200915/time-leave-queen-barbados-become-republic-2021>

¹⁵ https://www.huffpost.com/entry/barbados-removes-nelson-statue-break-colonial-past_n_5fb3e4e9c5b6aad41f735c16

In the Antigua that I knew, we lived on a street named after an English maritime criminal, Horatio Nelson, and all the other streets around us were named after some other English maritime criminals. There was Rodney Street, there was Hood Street, there was Hawkins Street, and there as Drake Street (24). ...In the middle of High Street was the Barclays Bank. The Barclay brothers, who started Barclays Bank, were slave-traders. That is how they made their money. When the English outlawed the slave trade, the Barclay brothers went into banking. (25-26)

This allows us to put into relief the decisions of Barbadian Prime Minister Mottley, who quoted the Caribbean Island nation's first premier, Errol Barrow, who warned against "loitering on colonial premises" and as such instituted a series of overt decolonial moves. With an eye to the still left unresolved issues of colonially-created economic gaps in the Caribbean at the start of the postcolonial state, Prime Minister Mia Mottley's participation in the Reparations forum on July 6, 2020, and as Chair of CARICOM represented well the interests of the Caribbean community as it relate to the economic recuperations implied in reparations debates. There she emphasized that there was no "development compact" after emancipation, which left the Caribbean depleted and without economic resources after "flag independence" i.e. with political independence but lacking resources to rise to the stability after hundreds of years of European extractive colonialism. Relatedly, the transfer of Barbados to republican status happened in November 2021 with all the necessary pageantry indicating another success of the Mia Mottley tenure followed by a sweeping unprecedented unanimous victory at the polls. Major tasks of transformative leadership are being advanced by Mia Mottley giving us new paradigms of leadership worth emulating on the global level.

Conclusion: Institutional Semi-Colonies

I agree with Ngugi wa Thiong'o prime asserter of an early abolition discourse and the decolonizing the mind. [The classic project by Ngugi wa Thiong'o, Taban lo Lyiong and others which is a staple in African literary studies "On the Abolition of the English Department" presented on the 20th of September, 1968 at the University of Nairobi, Kenya].¹⁶

The whole world needs decolonization, because in so many ways, the modern world was formed by forces of economic, political and cultural colonialism. The colonizer and the colonized were affected in different ways by the colonial process. We have to work for a decolonized world."

¹⁶ Published subsequently in his book *Homecoming* and later in *a Postcolonial Studies reader*, it remains a signature document of its era. In *Decolonizing the Academy. African Diaspora Studies* (2003).

So how do we repair this damage and continue the unfinished or “arrested” decolonization project; thereby to reclaim some of the lost direction, go back to our map as it were.¹⁷

In the introduction to *Decolonizing the Academy* (2003), an intellectual project developed to place African Diaspora Studies as one of the major vectors of the unfinished decolonizing process, I asserted that the academy, the university and the larger knowledge production apparatus is perhaps one of the most colonized of spaces. In every discipline, one is confronted with a production of knowledge that assumes European epistemologies, ideas, timelines as the defining frameworks for intellectual work. This thereby creates a hierarchy of knowledge in which African peoples experiences still remain at the bottom, or outside of consideration.

Many countries are only now changing street names as often in the US, names and statuary representations sometimes of people who worked against our freedom, were enslavers, pirates, colonizers remain visible. A task force to study how to change those names and what to do with the statues to colonizers and pirates was recently formed in Trinidad; in Martinique young people have simply started taking them down sometimes with criminal penalties by semi-colonial leadership.

We can assert as well that the entire academic enterprise in the Anglo-American university operates on similar terms. The ubiquity of English Departments may be the most prominent colonial sign at the academic level, a remaining colonial institution, the centerpiece of the humanities in most institutions, meant to initiate students into the hierarchy of literary knowledge, Western literary culture and its dominance. English Departments have tended to be linked to the advancement, maintenance and acceptance of the culture of the British Empire and thereby one of those institutions complicit in maintaining dominant structural inequities by the very nature of their naming and orientations in terms of what they teach and how they teach that literature. Colonial statues standing in plain site in most universities.

The point about the “Coloniality of knowledge” as defined by Quijano/Mignolo (2002) is that the “The expansion of Western capitalism implied the expansion of Western epistemology in all its ramifications, from the instrumental reason that went along with capitalism and the industrial revolution to the theories of the state, to the criticism of both capitalism and the state” (59).

The British colonial project and its unresolved issues in the Caribbean, Africa, India and even Israel and Palestine, the absence of reparations for the exploited labor; U.S. economic backyarding involvement in the Caribbean and central America for sure; the settler-colonial destruction of indigenous peoples; the economic abandonment of the Caribbean except for pleasure and/or exploitation of its resources and people and so on. All of these need further analyses by economists and political scientists to identify the specific nature of continuing neo-colonial operations and the various existing neo-colonies, beyond the Lenin identification discussed above. The various recent coups in Africa – Mali, Niger, Guinea, Chad, Burkina Faso, Niger -- have revealed that French colonial operations continued in full and plain sight often with the collusion of neo-colonial leaders with these two politics enriching themselves on the resources of these countries while continuing

¹⁷ Ngugi wa Thiong’o on Decolonization, *Presence Africaine* 197 (2019).

rank exploitation, the same exploitation for the benefit of European populations identified by Winston Churchill as cited by Beckles (2021) as the bases for reparative justice. What has been revealed is a specific kind of African neo-colonialism that Kwame Nkrumah had identified.

What is under our control, though often still a site of necessary contestation, in the institutional academic context in which we work is the knowledge production area – the epistemic therefore. So in the search for new language, we recognize as well that there are some terms which got left behind. The semi-colony is one of those useful terms that for me still has meaning and application.

The university as it exists today maintained the same colonial structures, it inherited, whether in the U.S., the Caribbean or Africa. We operate still in the academy, new and continuing questions need to emerge then that must be brought forward for every generation: How to ensure that all students are exposed to a range of knowledges as they make their way through the institution? How to restructure and move out of that order of knowledge in which a series of other humans and the work they have produced, their epistemologies and ontological systems remain outside of the frames of importance in the larger institutional contexts? For this scholar, updating Said then, it is significant to pursue these understandings in the process of advancing knowledge where there still remains an incomplete knowledge acquisition process; that continued epistemic violence on our students unless we are able to account for missing areas of study. how does a university respond to its community's needs?

We navigate always between, on the one hand a past of dignity and legendary greatness; on the other the starkness of the initial history of dispossession, economic difficulty, brought on sometimes by horrendous leadership, often in collusion with external actors; environment, climate, location. But through it all there remains an amazing resistance of its people matched by an outstanding creativity. We live with a series of conflicting representations, but above all a definition of an unrelenting humanity which is at the core of most inter-human relations. From what it takes to survive in the harshest conditions, to how one begins again after everything falls apart; to how one lives a life of beauty and joy in spite of institutional and state level attempts at continued subordination.

References

Baugh, Eddie. "Poetry as Ritual: Reading Kamau Brathwaite," *Journal of West Indian Literature* 8:1(October, 1998):1-9.

Beckles, Hilary. *How Britain Underdeveloped the Caribbean*. The University of the West Indies Press, 2021.

Boggs, James. "Manifesto for a Black Revolutionary Party" (1969).

- Boyce Davies, Carole. "From Post-Coloniality to Uprising Textualities," in *Black Women, Writing and Identity. Migrations of the Subject*. London: Routledge, 1994.
- Boyce Davies, Carole. *Black Women's Rights. Leadership and the Circularities of Power*. Rowman and Littlefield, Lexington Books, 2022.
- Boyce Davies, Carole ed. *Claudia Jones. Beyond Containment*. Banbury: Ayebia, 2011.
- Boyce Davies, Carole and Monica Jardine. "Imperial Geographies and Caribbean Nationalism: At The Border Between *A Dying Colonialism* And U.S. Hegemony." *Centennial Review* (3:3, Fall, 2003): 151-174.
- Boyce Davies, Carole. *Caribbean Spaces*. University of Illinois Press, 2013.
- Brathwaite, Edward (Kamau). "Negus." *The Arrivants*. Oxford University Press, 1978: 222-224).
- DuBois, W.E.B. *A Small Nation of People. W.E.B. DuBois and African American Portraits of Progress* with essays by David Levering Lewis and Deborah Willis Amistad, 2003.
- Carpentier, Alejo. *The Kingdom of This World*. 1949. Farrar, Strauss and Giroux, 2006).
- Getachew, Adom. *Worldmaking after Empire: The Rise and Fall of Self-Determination*. Princeton, 2019.
- Kincaid, Jamaica. *A Small Place*. Farrar, Strauss & Giroux, 1988.
- Lenin, Vladimir. *Imperialism, the Highest Stage of Capitalism*. 1917.
- Marshall, Paule. *The Chosen Place, The Timeless People*. New York: Vintage, 1984.
- Mbembe, Achille. "Notes on the Post Colony." *Africa: Journal of the International African Institute*, 62: 1 (1992): 3-37.
- Nkrumah, Kwame. *Neocolonialism, The Last Stage of Capitalism*. (1966). <https://www.marxists.org/ebooks/nkrumah/nkrumah-neocolonialism.pdf>
- Palmer, Colin. *Eric Williams and the Making of the Modern Caribbean*. University of North Carolina Press, 2009.
- Quijano, Annibal. "Coloniality of Power, Eurocentricism and Latin America." *Nepantla. Views from the South*. 1:3(2000): 533-580.
- Quijano, Annibal and Walter D. Mignolo. "The Geopolitics of Knowledge and the Colonial Difference." *The South Atlantic Quarterly* 101:1(Winter, 2002): 57-96.
- Rodney, Walter. (1976) "Decolonization" *Decolonial Marxism*. Verso, 2022.

Sheller, Mimi. "Caribbean Futures in the Offshore Anthropocene: Debt, Disaster, and Duration." *Society and Space*, 36(6): 2018: 971-986.

Taiwo, Olufemi. *Elite Capture*. Haymarket Books, 2022.

Tamale, Sylvia. *Decolonization and Afro-Feminism*. Ottawa: Daraja Press, 2020.

Tuck, Eve and K.WayneYang. "Decolonization is Not a Metaphor." *Decolonization: Indigeneity, Education & Society* Vol. 1, No. 1, 2012, pp. 1-40.

Turner, James. "Black Cities. Colonies or City States" *Blacks In The Cities: Land And Self-Determination*. Special issue of *The Black Scholar*, April 1970, 1: 6: 9-13.

Wa Thiong'o, Ngũgĩ. *Decolonising the Mind*. The Politics of Language in African Literature. Heinemann: 1986:16.

We Charge Genocide: The Historic Petition to the United Nations for Relief From a Crime of The United States Government Against the Negro People" (1951).

Conflict of interest

The author declares that she has no conflict of interest.

